

PROBONO

D8.9 Capacity building programme report (I)

PROBONO - The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods - has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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*The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient
buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods*

Deliverable n°:	D8.9
Deliverable name:	Capacity building programme report (I)
Version:	1.0
Release date:	04/12/2024
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Peer-reviewed
Author:	University College Dublin - Miriam Victoria Fernandez Lins

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	15/11/2024	First draft version	Miriam V. Fernandez Lins, Joselyn Lopez Pelayo, Philip Crowe.
0.5	30/10/2025	50% Deliverable	Miriam V. Fernandez Lins
0.8	18/11/2024	100% Deliverable	Miriam V. Fernandez Lins
0.9	2/12/2024	100% Deliverable +Peer & QM Reviews	María Jiménez Madlen Schmudde
1.0	4/12/2024	Final adjustments + QM/Coordinator Review + Final Submission	Miriam V. Fernandez Lins Georgia Pantelide

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
WP2 / T2.4, T2.5
WP1 / T1.3
WP 8 / T8.3

DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACE	de l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole
ACRB	Aarhus Centre for Regenerative Build
BIPV	Building Integrated Photovoltaics
BAPV	Building Attached Photovoltaics
CA	Consortium Agreement
CERNA	Climate and Energy Related Norms and Awareness
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DLRCOCO	Dun Laoghaire Rathdown County Council
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Green House Gases
IT	Information Technology
LL	Living Lab
PC	Project Coordinator
PCM	Phase Change Materials
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
POE	Post Occupancy Evaluation
PS	Project Secretariat
QM	Quality Management
SC	Scientific Coordinator
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader

Acronym	Description
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

This report offers a collation of activities, tools and other innovations that can contribute to PROBONO's Living Labs' Capacity Building. The scope is to review existing education and awareness raising initiatives or tools at different levels within the LLs. The objective is to set a baseline for a future suite of Capacity Building Tools, identifying strategies that can be adapted and/or scaled up to promote awareness, education, and behavioural change towards energy efficiency and further pro-environmental attitudes.

The findings from this report relate to WP2, more specifically to D2.5 - Collaborative Engagement Tools for Multi-Stakeholder Innovation (II), which explores the IT tools, focusing on the ones that were adopted in the Living Labs for their Social Innovation activities. Such IT tools are highly relevant to the building capacity in each LL because they can facilitate the continuity of communication, awareness raising, community engagement and behavioural change interventions.

Moreover, the baseline presented in this report provides valuable information on which approaches are useful for different scales and levels of governance or for addressing distinct types of challenges. For the next steps, selected initiatives will be scaled-up, being tested in wider populations seeking to bring evidence about their capacity to promote meaningful communication and behavioural change. The lessons learnt from the experiences of the Living Labs will inform PROBONO's partners and support the development of a suite of Capacity Building Tools in the project's future stages. The ultimate goal is that such a suite supports sustainable initiatives after the PROBONO project is completed, promoting continued and sustainable competence set in stakeholders.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 8.3. Capacity building on project findings (M1-M60)	<p>ST8.3.1 Set the tools baseline. Review existing education and awareness raising initiatives or tools at different governance levels to identify gaps for the wider context of each LL; gaps will be identified via a randomised controlled trial (online or field experiment) testing PROBONO findings about behaviour change for a sample of citizens from the wider community. Create the tools baseline, gathering data from WP2 and WP7 to help understand citizen/user behaviour and to identify the key social innovations representing the state of the art. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p> <p>ST8.3.2 Co-create a suite of Capacity Building tools. Create a suite of tools and initiatives to facilitate the uptake of the project findings at different governance levels, from the local Living Lab to city, regional, national and EU levels. The suite of tools for education and awareness raising initiatives for behaviour change will be co-created between partners and communities to meet the identified gaps for different communities of interest and/or demographics. Tools may include short animations, storytelling workshops, serious games, interactive learning tools, a travelling or online exhibition, or augmented reality. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p>	D2.5 Chapters 2 and 3.	D2.5 builds on the work of D2.4 which established a baseline of IT collaborative tools. In D2.5, chapter 2 and 3 explore how this applies to each LL which is highly relevant to building capacity in each LL.
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D8.9: Capacity building programme report (I)</p> <p>The aim of the Deliverable (GA) is to formulate the findings of T8.3 and explore step A) Report collating initial capacity building progress.</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverables & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The present deliverable reports on the findings and lessons learnt from the activities related to behaviour change and energy efficiency from WP2 and WP7. The purpose of this is to set a tools baseline, by providing a preliminary set of information that will be used for the next steps, when

these will be tested in a more general and larger population, aiming to develop a set of tools for education and awareness raising.

The task aims to understand how the Living Labs are conducting or are planning to conduct activities for energy efficiency and behaviour change. Furthermore, how the processes of developing such activities are improving the necessary skills, relationships and networks to implement and to scale-up actions for setting up a GBN, thus supporting a Just Climate Transition. This is a key factor to make the GBN sustainable after the PROBONO project is concluded, ensuring that the social and technical innovations developed are continually reviewed, adapted and increased in their positive impact.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverables

This document is organised in 9 chapters:

- Chapter 1 provides an Introduction, defines the purpose and scope of this document, maps PROBONO's Outputs, and identify interlinkages with other WPs of the project.
- Chapter 2 elaborates an overview of the Capacity Building concept, its relevance for the LLs, and a summary of the methods adopted for collecting the data reported in this document.
- Chapters 3 - 8 contains informs the activities developed in each of the six LLs, exploring their findings and lessons learnt.
- Chapter 9 presents the conclusion, summarising an overview of the findings and next steps for the project.

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

The findings of this deliverable provide relevant information for next steps of social activities, especially those relating to awareness and behaviour change towards energy efficiency. Significantly, they map the initial actions in this matter and will serve as basis for further planning and implementation of testing and scaling up across the living labs. Building on this, there will be the creation of a sustainable framework for actions that can occur after the PROBONO project is completed.

2 Capacity building in PROBONO's Living Labs

2.1 Overview

The initiatives related to behaviour change and energy efficiency are in the stage of planning or initial implementation in the PROBONO's Living Labs. While they assume a variety of formats and strategies, such initiatives have the common goal of establishing awareness and impact in users addressing to the human component of change. This means that the technology implemented through the PROBONO project is not only acknowledged by users and stakeholders from the project, but that they constitute pathways to promote a larger impact on the general public. This is very important for bringing meaningful contributions that can address the challenges of the Climate Transition in the scale that is urgently needed.

2.2 Methodology of data collection

The presented data was initially collected from the information material related to the initiatives or tools for behaviour change and energy efficiency presented in the WP2 and WP7 deliverables. After this first action, the Living Labs were invited to collaborate to the collation by confirming, adding, and updating the content about the initiatives that were carried out or that are planned. Discussions were carried out in meetings, aiming to identify possibilities and limitations of actions and ideas.

3 Dublin LL Capacity building

3.1 Dublin GBN Vision

The Dublin Living Lab will be a sustainable, cost-effective, and zero-carbon Green Building Neighbourhood, networking key municipal buildings and optimising prototypical housing retrofit for future wider replication. The Living Lab will engage local citizens in the design and development of a green town centre and living neighbourhood. The primary goal is to improve energy performance by considering energy inefficiency in older municipal buildings. Each of the buildings in the GBN area is interlinked by their proximity, work, administration and importance to the community, business, and tourism in the area. At the centre of this area is County Hall, where all administrative work is carried out and the local council functions.

3.2 Post-Occupancy Evaluation in Beaufort, Dún Laoghaire

The Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE) is a study consisting of a focus group and survey, which aims to gather and disseminate feedback from tenants of Beaufort Elderly Social Housing on their experience of undergoing a retrofit of their homes while in situ. University College Dublin conducted this study in collaboration with Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council.

The Irish Government has set a target for local authorities in Ireland to retrofit 500,000 social housing units by 2030. As part of meeting their targets, Dun Laoghaire Rathdown County Council (DLRCOCO) decided to retrofit 54 units from Beaufort Elderly Social Housing in 2022. There are some significant challenges to retrofitting social housing in Ireland, one being finding alternative locations for tenants to live during the retrofit, which is difficult due to lack of alternative accommodation and costs associated. This is why the Housing Maintenance department in DLRCOCO decided to take the unique approach of retrofitting social housing while the tenants remained in situ.

However, little is understood of what that experience was like for the tenants. Therefore, as DLRCOCO plans to undertake more in-situ retrofits, the POE will provide crucial feedback and recommendations on how to improve the process for tenants. There was no PROBONO budget required to carry out this study.

The following objectives were established for the POE:

1. Hold two focus group sessions to gather qualitative data.

2. Follow up with in-depth surveys to gather quantitative data.
3. Compile the data and analyse for findings.
4. Draw up a report containing the findings and distribute it to DLRCOCO.
5. Present the report and findings to the Housing Maintenance Manager in DLRCOCO.

Tools and methods adopted were:

- Qualitative data has been collected via two rounds of focus groups.
- Quantitative data has been collected through in-depth surveys with self-selected participants.

As its KPI, the focus group hold two sessions and follow-up with in depth surveys of 6 people.

The expected timeline was to have the study completed by December 2023. However, it was November 2024 when the study was completed. The reasons for this are outlined below and provide relevant lessons for Capacity Building.

- Having the right personnel available at the right time proved to be a challenge for this study. Coordinating between key people involved in the study and adjusting to their availability created some delay in carrying out the study.
- Gathering important information and gaining approval to carry out the study was a challenge. This was due to a busy schedule for the person responsible for approval who also had the information needed.
- There is a general challenge when trying to coordinate a study between two separate organisations. Access to information and key personnel can be difficult.
- Advertising the focus groups to participants was a challenge due to the nature of the study and research ethics rules.

Findings from this study are currently being analysed and will be reported on in D8.10. The review of the Beaufort POE is currently ongoing and will be reported on in D8.10. The data will be analysed and formulated into findings and recommendations, which will then be disseminated to key personnel at DLRCOCO.

DLRCOCO is planning to carry out further in-situ retrofits. This provides an opportunity to carry out further POEs and to expand the scope of the studies to include pre and post-retrofit viewpoints. This activity is also relevant to the WP2 activities.

3.3 Installation of Photo Voltaic Panels

Dublin LL has been currently selecting areas for installation of Photo Voltaic Panels within the GBN, these panels are incorporated to the façade of public buildings, more specifically, the DLR County Hall and the Lexlcon Library (Figure 1). The goals are twofold: first it is to cut CO2 emissions and in the case of the Lexlcon directly offset current fossil fuel use, since it adopts a wood burner. The second goal is to take advantage of the visibility that such panels would have to encourage individuals and businesses to also adopt this type of technology.

Figure 1: Visual representation of Building Integrated Photo Voltaic proposed to be installed in the Lexlcon Library

These panels will serve as the primary source of GHG emission reduction within the Dublin LL thanks to their production of clean energy. In the case of the Lexlcon library, BIPV panels will allow for the generation of around 27 MWh/a of renewable energy, which will support the LL to reach the KPI's of 60% reduction in GHG emissions and 40% improvement towards NZEB. This will allow the building to become aligned with PROBONO emission factor targets by the year 2027.

An additional benefit has been identified regarding the library, thanks to its dominating presence in the DLR skyline and its public popularity. The building was completed in 2014 and received a mixed reaction. However, over the previous decade, it has become a true icon of the town. It currently holds an array of cultural events and will host the PROBONO Dublin LL GBN Hub.

For these reasons, we expect the presence of BIPV in the LexIcon library to have a very large positive public impact and promote the GBN Hub. The following images 3 illustrate how the panels would be integrated into the building, in the rooftop (Figure 2) and in the facades (Figure 3) with visibility for the public.

Figure 2: Building Adjacent Photo Voltaic proposed to be installed in County Hall

Figure 3: Building Integrated Photo Voltaic proposed to be installed in County Hall

County Hall, the LL’s flagship building, will additionally receive BIPV on two facades alongside traditional BAPV on the rooftop. This will yield a total output of around 92 MWh/a. County Hall

remains the most energy intensive building in the LL, so was targeted as a flagship building. This also came with the benefit of allowing the Council to lead by example, promoting the use of these technologies to external stakeholders such as the public and private industry. Additionally, these panels are crucial to the function of other interventions within the GBN. The power produced by these panels will feed into the planned Battery Bank and Bi-Directional EV chargers, strengthening the use cases of all interventions.

The installation of these panels on County Hall will allow for achieving both the PROBONO GHG emissions and emissions factor targets for County Hall by the years 2026 and 2031, respectively.

These estimates remain conservative, as they do not account for the other planned interventions in the LL, such as the battery bank, bi-direction EV charging, upgrades to the County Hall roof membrane and others. There is, hence, a high likelihood that these targets will be reached ahead of the current estimated date.

All estimates were provided thanks to input from Fraunhofer, SolarEvolution, the DLRCOCO building management team and SOPREMA.

For this installation to take place, several agreements within the Council and with technology providers have been made or are in the process of negotiations. The installation of the rooftop PV in County Hall will take place in Partnership with the Energy Performance Contractor, CODEMA. Since energy upgrades are already taking place, this team has assisted in the planning and will assist in the construction work to take place over the coming months.

This is especially important regarding the purchasing of panels. This team will assist in the tendering process required for both the BIPV and BAPV. Inputs from all partners will be collected for the required panel specifications, which will allow tendering and subsequent purchases to take place in the most efficient manner possible for the LL.

The current estimated costs for all systems, including labour, are 637,000€ for County Hall, and 500,000€ for the Lexicon Library, for a total expenditure of 1,138,000€ of photovoltaic panels in the LL within the scope of PROBONO.

The current timeline has been pushed back several times due to the ongoing work around securing a budget amendment from the European Commission. However, the procurement process has begun, with a launch expected before Christmas. From here, prerequisites such as the rooftop membrane and ballast installation will begin concurrently with the procurement process. Once procurement is complete and the panels have been purchased, the installation work is expected to take around one month to complete. After the panels are in place, additional

work around wiring and integration with the EMS and Digital twin systems will begin. The complete installation process will be completed by the end of year 2025, with an optimistic timeline placing the finishing date around October.

Challenges have been raised around the energy production potential of the panels. Since County Hall is a very energy intensive building, the original interventions were deemed as leaving too large a risk of not achieving KPIs. The amendment process was, therefore, initiated. Around governance, the primary challenge was the change in ownership of the Ferry Terminal. This building was originally to be part of the LL but was later dropped due to issues with leaseholders. The decision was therefore made to include the Library in the LL.

Once the panels are in place and monitoring is completed. The Dublin LL wished to disseminate its results to other Local Authorities around the country. It is hoped that due to each authority being held to a Climate Action Plan, there will be resources available to replicate the interventions in front of Dublin LL. Dissemination will also take place for the public and private industries. Several pre-existing associations and relationships will be used in this context, such as relations with Microsoft and MasterCard in the Sandyford Business district. This will also serve as an opportunity for the Council to show not only PROBONO interventions but results from other ongoing projects within Dun Laoghaire Rathdown, such as the Living Streets project, Smart Parks, Bathing Water Quality and Accessible parking.

In conclusion, the integration of Building Integrated and Building Adjacent Photo Voltaic (BIPV and BAPV) panels at Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Hall and the LexIcon Library marks a significant step toward reducing carbon emissions and demonstrating the potential of renewable energy solutions. By transforming these prominent public buildings into visible examples of sustainable energy, the project aims to inspire broader adoption among individuals and businesses. The planned Geodesign and Open House 2025 will serve as the primary platforms to create awareness around these interventions.

Additionally, this initiative offers a scalable model for other local authorities and organisations across Ireland. By leveraging the knowledge gained and partnerships established, such as those with Fraunhofer and CODEMA, the project can serve as a blueprint for replicating these interventions and accelerating progress toward climate action goals nationwide.

3.4 Conclusion

Dublin Living Lab has carried out a set of activities that have been contributing significantly to its capacity building. Significantly, lessons learnt from Beaufort POE can potentially be used to improve DLR's approaches towards retrofit works and it can also be explored in larger scale activities further on.

4 Madrid LL Capacity building

4.1 Madrid GBN Vision

Madrid Living Lab is in Las Tablas Oeste Area, within Madrid Nuevo Norte development plan. This area is the first to be urbanised and it consists of four main activities: Design of the urbanisation project, Execution of the urbanisation project, Buildings' design and Execution of the buildings. PROBONO's activities will focus on increasing the energy efficiency in the buildings, with the main innovation being the development of a Geothermal District Heating and Cooling in public spaces.

4.2 CERNA Survey

With the primary aim of assessing the knowledge of citizens regarding energy efficiency and sustainable practices, the CERNA Survey also informs the strategy for communicating activities that improve the citizens' attitudes related to energy performance in buildings.

The survey was planned in two rounds and managed by a market research company. The first round was launched in the city of Madrid, in March 2024 and the second one is to be launched in spring 2026. The survey is focused on investigating three main topics: awareness of the most effective actions to save energy, perceived norms, and pluralistic ignorance. So, the final analysis of the results will allow conclusions on the next actions to undertake in order to improve citizens' aptitude toward energy efficiency.

Hamilton was the company awarded for the service, and the budget for the subcontracting was 1.950€ without VAT. The service was developed through online interviews with a questionnaire, previously structured and programmed by SIN, with an approximate length between 10 and 15 minutes. The entire process was smoothly led, and it is recommendable to be replicated on other LLs.

The results of the CERNA can be integrated under the Digital Twin, and further conversations about this possibility will be planned in the coming months

Presently, the Madrid LL team, with the support of SIN as WP2 leader, is studying the best way to disseminate CERNA results in Madrid.

4.3 Citizen Engagement Activities

Two initiatives in Madrid Living Lab are engaging citizens. The first one took place on November 15, 2023, in Las Tablas, Madrid.

First Initiative

The Citizen Engagement Workshop, part of the Madrid Nuevo Norte project, aimed to involve residents in managing community energy infrastructures. The workshop featured presentations on the PROBONO project, Green Building Neighbourhoods, and survey results regarding community energy preferences (Figure 4, Figure 5). The workshop gathered mainly attendees from Ministry of Ecology Transition, from Madrid Regional Government in particular Ecology transition and Circular Economy area, the Diversification and Energy Saving National Institute, Madrid City Council and District Heating and Cooling Network association. 32 participants took place to the workshop.

Figure 4: Work Groups during the workshop in Madrid in November 2023

Figure 5: WP1 leader speaking during the workshop in Madrid in November 2023

Second Initiative

The second citizen engagement initiative will take place next spring, 2025. It intends to be a participatory Codesign process to design the area located below the bridge connecting the PROBONO area with the adjacent neighbourhood. The site is a residual area, and citizen participation is required to convert it into a useful space for the community. The process will take place as a workshop where actors from different stakeholder' groups and interests will be invited. The co-design process will rely mainly on a digital tool, likely SuperBarrio, in order to engage a broad spectrum of stakeholders, get a higher level of engagement, and ensure inclusivity. Superbarrio is a Co-design tool that is location-specific where participants are offered a set of solutions to choose from and locate their choices in the designated area of discussion. It has a very intuitive interface, using 3D modelling. Moreover, login is optional. It is optimal for small (plot-size) scales. The tool is open source and was developed by IAAC, where we asked for information on how it could be adapted to the Madrid LL case.

Activities are supported by SIN and UCD designing the whole workshop. A social expert bringing experience and sound knowledge of the Superbarrio will be contacted in order to support the event and address the process for the IT tool.

It is expected to unveil criteria and milestone to address the architects' design and obtain a space hinge that meet citizen's needs.

4.4 Conclusion

Social innovation initiatives in GBN are an important pillar for Madrid Nuevo Norte implementation, aiming to find out the sensitivity of citizens in order to incorporate it into the

design of the urban development projects that will define the future neighbourhood in the north of Madrid.

It highlights the innovative and socially sustainable vision of this major urban transformation project, which promotes a new type of urban planning that incorporates citizens to build a truly new model of a 21st century city.

In 2021, Madrid Nuevo Norte simultaneously obtained the LEED for Communities Plan and Design sustainability pre-certification with a “Gold” level, as well as the BREEAM ES Urbanismo 2020 provisional certificate, the two most prestigious sustainability seals worldwide. With this recognition, Madrid Nuevo Norte became an international pioneer, being the first urban development project in Europe to obtain both provisional certificates, making it an international benchmark in the field of sustainable urban development.

In order to obtain these pre-certifications and to obtain the definitive certifications, citizen participation work is essential, since both seals highly value participatory processes.

5 Porto LL Capacity building

5.1 Porto GBN Vision

Porto Living Lab aims for developing a GBN within SONAE campus, its community and opening to external stakeholders for testing social and technical sustainable solutions. Another important aspect of its approach is the boosting of biodiversity on campus, with natural green spaces that also promote the wellbeing of employees. Currently, the innovations for behaviour change related to energy efficiency are small scale and SONAE/Capwatt, together with CARTIF, are considering a KPI for scaling-up.

5.2 Smart Street

The Smart Street is an area of the campus designated to bring awareness and education on topics of energy, biodiversity and community. It is configured as a street that is very central to the campus, close to a historical structure that was renovated for hosting experimental projects that will be converted into a space for visitors. Some assets related to energy were already implemented around this area, such as PVs on carports and roofs, PV trackers and Energy Storage systems. The projects planned within PROBONO for this highly visible area are to be completed in 2024-2025 and consist of a Cool Roof test with bi-facial PV, Mobility Solutions and BIPV. Partners involved are Capwatt, SOPREMA, Bovlabs and Fraunhofer.

In the Smart Street, various biodiversity-related projects were implemented, including a pond, nest boxes to encourage nesting, a butterfly garden, dry stone walls and cairns, gardens, as well as benches and signage with positive messages explaining the benefits of reducing grass mowing. The pond has been colonised by frogs and newts, and over time, other species have appeared, indicating that this space is a great success in supporting the environment and promoting biodiversity.

Figure 6: Biodiversity at Smart Street

The main objective of Smart Street is to transform a street into an innovative space where the Campus community and visitors get into contact with design solutions for biodiversity, energy and community.

5.3 Mobility Initiatives (Smart EV Hub, Solar 2 Vehicle, and Vehicle 2 Grid)

Within the PROBONO project, a Smart EV Hub is being developed at the SONAE Campus to optimise EV charging by integrating variables such as power availability, renewable energy sources (RES), market prices, and user preferences into an efficient management algorithm. Additionally, the Solar 2 Vehicle system leverages PV energy to directly charge electric vehicles, synchronising charging times with renewable energy production to reduce grid dependency. The goal is to use an electric vehicle as a dynamic energy storage unit, enabling it to store surplus energy and reinject it back into the grid when needed. This technology supports a range of grid services, enhances grid stability, and provides added value to the EV owner and the energy system.

These initiatives will act as small-scale pilots, enabling the evaluation of the technology's feasibility and potential for scaling across other locations within the SONAE ecosystem. Additionally, the projects aim to encourage energy companies operating on Campus to integrate these innovative solutions into their portfolio of services. Given the transformative nature of the mobility market, the implementation on campus will also serve as an educational opportunity, equipping Campus employees with valuable insights and knowledge about advanced mobility solutions.

5.4 Renewable Energy Community (REC)

The Renewable Energy Community (REC) at Porto Living Lab aims to offer a scalable and practical solution to collective energy consumption. By focusing on locally generated renewable energy, the initiative fosters community-based energy management. At the SONAE Campus, the REC serves as a testbed for developing governance frameworks, energy-sharing mechanisms, and best practices that can be adapted to different contexts. Key lessons will be drawn from the experience, including strategies for stakeholder engagement, effective community involvement, and methods for optimising energy management. These insights will be valuable for other communities or organisations aiming to establish similar RECs. Additionally, collaboration with other Living Labs, such as Brussels, will enable sharing of best practices and methodologies, advancing the implementation of renewable energy solutions at a larger scale.

5.5 Photovoltaic-related innovations (Cool Roof with Bifacial PV and Building Integrated Photovoltaics)

The integration of PV technology into the campus buildings is aimed at improving energy efficiency and providing a sustainable energy solution for the Campus. Lessons learned from this initiative will help identify the most effective installation practices, performance metrics, and potential for integration with other renewable energy systems. The data and insights gathered can be shared with other Living Labs, smart cities, and green building projects, providing a roadmap for deploying PV systems in urban environments. As a result, these innovations have the potential to be replicated and scaled in other regions, accelerating the adoption of clean energy technologies and contributing to broader sustainability goals.

5.6 Storage Solutions (Second-Life Batteries and Phase Change Materials)

The use of second-life batteries and Phase Change Materials (PCMs) in energy storage at Porto Living Lab offers valuable insights into their effectiveness for renewable energy integration. Lessons learned from the deployment of these pilots will help assess their viability for large-scale energy storage, enabling more sustainable grid management. The potential for scalability is significant, as these solutions can be replicated in other communities or urban areas looking to optimise their energy storage systems. These storage innovations could support the transition to more flexible, sustainable, and energy-efficient communities.

5.7 CERNA Survey

The CERNA survey is designed to investigate three main topics: awareness of the most effective energy-saving actions, perceived norms, and pluralistic ignorance. Conducted by SIN, the survey took place in March 2024, with 117 respondents from SONAE Campus. After thorough data cleaning — removing data from participants who did not pass the attention check or completed the survey too quickly — 83 valid responses were retained.

Results show misconceptions about effective environmental actions and that participants support climate initiatives but believe others, especially on a national level, are less supportive. Social norms in close personal circles were also found to strongly influence climate attitudes.

The full results can be found in deliverable D2.6, “Social and Behavioral Implementation (I)”.

The CERNA survey serves as a valuable tool for guiding the development of communication strategies. Analysing the results enables the design of targeted initiatives aimed at enhancing citizens' attitudes and awareness regarding energy performance.

5.8 Vegetable garden

The vegetable garden has been part of Porto Living Lab since 2022 and serves as a hub for solidarity, team building, learning and empowerment of the communities through the donation of all vegetables. Between April 2022 and November 2024, the project achieved significant milestones, including the establishment of 30 cultivation beds, the donation of 1 ton of vegetables, the saving of 160,000 litres of water, the absorption of 2 tons of CO₂, and the reuse of 500 kg of organic waste through composting. Monthly, theoretical, and practical training sessions are conducted in the vegetable garden for volunteers who are employees of Sonae Campus companies. These sessions are supported by external experts from Noocity, ensuring a comprehensive learning experience.

This project fosters sustainable habits by encouraging employees to adopt organic cultivation methods without fertilisers, promoting lasting environmental responsibility.

Figure 7: Vegetable garden

5.9 House of Birds

At Sonae Campus, it has been installed 25 birdhouses throughout the Campus to provide native birds with a safe environment for settling and reproduction. The main objective is to promote identification and biodiversity among our employees (~3.500 people).

SONAE will continue to create opportunities for employees and children to engage in workshops and sessions that raise awareness about sustainability issues. The aim is to encourage a sense of responsibility toward protecting birds and supporting their nesting process, fostering lasting environmental care.

Figure 8: House of Birds

5.10 Social Innovation and Open Community Lab

The Social Innovation and Open Community Lab intends to be an open experimentation laboratory designed to test and evaluate innovative solutions in sustainability, with a focus on energy, biodiversity, and circularity.

This initiative aims to promote collaboration between Sonae, universities, research centres, and startups or companies, creating a dynamic environment for the development and implementation of more responsible and environmentally friendly practices. Through synergy among various partners, the Social Innovation and Open Community Lab aims to drive sustainable innovation by addressing social challenges, promoting collaborative learning, stimulating R&D activities, and contributing to the practical and experienced training of professionals committed to sustainability. The Social Innovation and Open Community Lab initiative launched its call for applications on 20 May 2024, inviting the community to explore sustainability solutions at Sonae Campus. An Open Day was held on 4 June, allowing visitors to explore the campus. The application period, initially from 20 May to 11 June, was extended to 18 June due to increased interest. After a thorough evaluation from 19 to 27 June, four projects were selected. On 28 June, two projects advanced to the implementation phase after feasibility assessments. One of the selected projects aims to drive behaviour change and raise awareness by offering workshops for the internal and external community, engaging employees and schools. These workshops focus on environmental education through hands-on activities, promoting the reuse of materials, environmental preservation, and conscious consumption.

5.11 Conclusion

The social innovation activities undertaken play a crucial role in Porto LL, as one of its primary objectives is to raise community awareness about sustainability and energy-related topics. These initiatives are directly related to promoting behaviour change and enhancing energy efficiency, thereby contributing to the LL's capacity building efforts. Through collaborative approaches, these innovations actively engage stakeholders, encouraging their involvement in the joint development and implementation of a more sustainable campus environment.

6 Brussels LL Capacity building

6.1 Brussels GBN Vision

The Brussels GBN vision focuses on creating energy-positive, zero-emission buildings through sustainable innovations like green roofs and energy monitoring. This project aims to catalyse the neighbourhood's dynamics, strengthen local links, and amplify social innovation through the school's pedagogy, making it a central hub for green energy initiatives. The strategy focuses on renovating the ACE school in Auderghem and promoting neighbourhood involvement to demonstrate the benefits of working with GBN. Social initiatives such as improving student mobility and safety are part of the green urban development framework.

The Brussels Living Lab “de l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole” (ACE) is located in the commune of Auderghem, on a primary road, and faces mobility challenges: road insecurity due to high intensity of motorised traffic, overspeeding, sub-optimal bicycle accesses, narrow roads and sidewalks, while the majority of students and staff come by bicycle and public transport. The mobility challenges facing the school are shared with all (local) stakeholders and revolve around two main objectives: *Mobility as a community builder*, which aims to foster integration and raise awareness within the neighbourhood, and *Mobility as a means to change behaviour*, focused on reducing speed and promoting sustainable mobility. To contextualise, achieving “vision zero” in the area and addressing the number of crashes around the school underline the urgency and shared commitment to these goals.

6.2 Mobility Week

From 16th to 22th September 2024, the Brussels Living Lab hosted the Mobility Week, promoting safe and sustainable mobility among students, educators, and the local community.

A self-reported survey and quick poll were conducted among school users and neighbourhood residents to measure the campaign's impact on behaviour and local traffic patterns. A traffic analyser was also installed to record motorised vehicle speeds, modal split, and traffic intensity before, during, and after the event.

This initiative encouraged participants to rethink mobility habits and environmental impact. By promoting active and safe transportation, the Mobility Week aimed to foster long-term

behaviour change. Benefits included a safer environment for the neighbourhood through decreased motorised traffic and speed-reducing measures on transit routes. The traffic analyser also allowed for an in-depth review of traffic flow, peak hours, and average speed, enabling comparisons with other schools and assessing changes during Mobility Week.

Tools and Methods implemented in this activity were:

- **Learning to Cycle in Traffic:** Second-year secondary students received a full day of cycling and traffic training from **Pro Velo**, an **external organisation** specialising in cycling education. The session focused on safe cycling practices, understanding traffic signs, hazard anticipation, urban cycling skills, and building students' confidence in daily bike use.

Figure 9: Students during mobility week, at “Learning to Cycle in Traffic” activity

- **Bicycle Repair Workshop:** Students learned essential bike maintenance and repair skills, fostering independence and the ability to maintain their transportation mode. This workshop aimed to equip students with the skills to ensure their bikes remain

dependable and ready for daily travel. A well-maintained bike is safer, more reliable, and encourages consistent use as a sustainable mode of transport.

Figure 10: Students during mobility week, at "Bike Repair" activity

- **Road Safety with the "Peacekeepers":** Throughout the week, fifth and sixth-grade students participated as "peacekeepers", standing at pedestrian crossings near the school. Their role was to increase visibility around the school and secure safe passage for pedestrians, particularly during morning and afternoon peak times. By taking on this responsibility, the Peacekeepers helped raise awareness of road safety and reinforced safe crossing practices for the entire school community.

Figure 11: Students during mobility week, at "Road Safety with the "Peacekeepers" activity

- **Bicycle Challenge – Atrium Photo:** This activity encouraged participants to bring as many bikes as possible to the atrium, celebrating efforts toward greener transportation.
- **Geography Observation Outing:** Geography classes took a new turn this week with an observation outing focused on local mobility infrastructure, prompting ideas for improvements to support active transportation.

Traffic Analyser (Fixed on Chaussée de Wavre with Telraam Technology):

A radar was installed in front of the ACE school to collect comprehensive data on traffic volumes, speeds, and the modal split, helping assess the Mobility Week's effectiveness.

KPIs considered in this activity are

- Attitude to come to school by bike or by foot (students)
- Travel safety perception (Students)
- Traffic composition
- Average speed motorised vehicles
- Traffic counts (light, heavy, bikes, M2W)

- Impact of mobility campaign on behaviour change

The Mobility Week was carried out in partnership with **ACE** and the **Vias Institute**, who provided support and expertise to maximize the impact of the initiative. The campaign relied on **existing resources** and required no additional operational budget, making it a sustainable model for future projects. The campaign ran from the 16th to the 22nd of **September 2024**, with evaluations conducted before and after to measure its effectiveness and gather feedback.

Looking ahead, this activity is set to be **replicated with greater involvement from neighbourhood residents** and enhanced with external rewards to further motivate participation.

6.3 Street and Alderman Interview

During the month of September, a street interview was carried out on the neighbourhood surrounding the ACE school. Also, a meeting with the Alderman of Auderghem took place.

A street interview provided neighbourhood residents an opportunity to share their views, gathering insights on travel habits, daily challenges, and ideas for improving local mobility. This listening initiative strengthened the connection between the school and its surrounding community. Considered KPIs were:

- Attitude to travel by bike or by foot (neighbourhood)
- Travel safety perception (neighbourhood)

Engaging public authorities is a key objective of the PROBONO project. That's why, at the beginning of September, Brussels' team met with the Auderghem alderman for mobility and the head of the municipal mobility department. This facilitated dialogue on mobility issues, road safety challenges, and explored how the municipality could support progress at the ACE level.

6.4 Conclusion

Brussels LL provide solid examples of how the social innovations of Green Building Neighbourhoods can be applied. The adoption of PROBONO's approach and innovations is proposed through a series of participatory methods that encourage stakeholders (including citizens) to take part in the co-design and co-delivery of a sustainable GBN.

7 Aarhus LL Capacity building

7.1 Aarhus GBN Vision

Aarhus University (AU) is currently undergoing a large-scale, university-wide renovation programme referred to as Campus 2.0 independently of PROBONO. The PROBONO Aarhus LL seeks to support this ambitious university agenda with targeted technological interventions in key locations that improve environmental, economic and social sustainability.

In addition, three social engagement activities have been pursued to boost local engagement, raise awareness of green interventions and opportunities amongst stakeholders, and to collect values, concepts and ideas from the local community. The activities are:

- Geodesign Workshop
- CERNA survey
- Engagement activities at the Regenerative Centre with external company NXT

The Geodesign workshop was conducted in April 2024 and is presented in detail in deliverable D2.5 *“Collaborative engagement tools for multi-stakeholder innovation”*.

7.2 CERNA Survey

A Climate and Energy Related Norms and Awareness (CERNA) survey will be conducted together with partner SIN, that will focus on energy and climate literacy (knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours related to energy), and mapping out misconceptions about others' knowledge and attitudes as well as social norms pertaining to the climate crisis and possible mitigation actions.

The original concept was that the communication and engagement strategy of Aarhus LL will be based on the data gathered through the distribution of the CERNA survey to university students and employees. The goal of the CERNA survey being conducted in the Aarhus LL is to understand the psychological factors that influence climate and energy-related behaviours in the student body at AU. This understanding is intended to support AU (as a client) in planning effective behavioural change interventions and policies, as argued by SIN to be necessary for building a Green Building Neighbourhood that prioritizes community participation and a willingness to adapt to pro-environmental norms and behaviours. The survey has been created in Alchemer

survey software, taking approximately 10-15 minutes to complete by participants, and was launched in mid 2024.

Unfortunately accessing stakeholders to complete the survey was found to be a complicated and difficult process, although numerous meetings were held with key student representatives. This has delayed the process. Currently a market research agency will be subcontracted to support the process of accessing suitable participants to complete the survey (acquiring data only; analysis will be subsequently conducted by SIN). A call for tenders was launched in October 2024 to three companies. The Aarhus LL and SIN are currently assessing the offers with the expectation that the survey will be completed early 2025. The CERNA survey will be repeated in 2026.

7.3 Engagement activities provided by NXT in the Aarhus Regenerative Centre

Aarhus University is establishing a new applied research centre dedicated to regenerative built environments, a paradigm in which new construction delivers a net positive impact on the climate and the environment. The thesis of the Aarhus Centre for Regenerative Building (ACRB) is that a large part of the green transition will be executed by commercial partners. Therefore, the centre is reaching out to the commercial sector by developing praxis-oriented, evidence-based knowledge to support decision making towards a regenerative future.

The Aarhus LL has a focus on (social) human-centred methods enhancing the effects developed ACRB, with the thesis that the same methods and potential effects will also be relevant for enhancing the social and networking potential of Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs) being built on human interaction and co-creation.

To boost and explore social engagement actions, Aarhus LL has partnered (via subcontract) with the company NXT to leverage their expertise in communicating complex ideas and building networks around social and environmental projects. This collaboration will focus on describing the social intervention and the *trigger effect* exemplified in the ACRB development and potential for empowering GBN development. We describe five example trigger events that are being explored together with NXT.

Trigger Event example 1 - weekly meeting:

Objective: to foster collaboration among experts from universities, the building industry, and the public sector to generate funding for (regenerative) applied research. By doing so, the aim is to create inclusiveness and maintain a focused dialogue, leading to the agency of members.

The potential effects of the interventions developed at the ACRB can be adapted and scaled to other types of collaborations (like a GBN)

Tasks: Demonstrate HOW meeting formats can be more effective. “Weekly meeting form” rethinking: Designing the Regenerative Meeting format narrative in a “manual” for inspiration.

Trigger Event example 2 - Regenerative Economy Session:

Objective: Discuss economic models that prioritise social well-being and sustainable development over traditional growth metrics. For example, adding risk analysis, avoiding emissions cost as a new variable, cost of reversed development reducing or avoiding climate tipping points, or taxonomy potential savings or real estate prices scenarios.

Tasks: Develop discussion topics that trigger and engage with participants. Coordinate the session with a link to a real-life case with the overall thinking on finding a desired future.

Trigger Event example 3 - Public Seminar:

Objective: Make scientific/economic/societal discussions on regenerative buildings accessible to a wider audience, “valorisation”, tools also addressing how much of the information is evidence based.

Tasks: The focus is not on the seminar itself, but rather on how to spread the core aims, and principles of ACRB, and the latest relevant research findings presented by invited speakers, to a broader audience (i.e. recent economic advances related to regenerative construction made accessible to the wider public; latest scientific developments made accessible to economic experts, etc.). This includes creating content for LinkedIn and relevant media with PROBONO information, a Google AI podcast production etc.

Trigger Event example 4 - Collaboration Platform:

Objective: Create a value for the members as individuals as well as co-create knowledge platforms to facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration among network members as well as displaying a joint created wider list of positive effects.

Tasks: Creating a prototype for assessing the peer reviewed positive pursuits and for regenerative development support (possibly AI powered) aggregating and prompting new needs with local attention (collaboration with UCD, potential software enhancement).

Trigger Event example 5 - Illustrative Report:

Objective: Relevance to other GBNs: The ACRB centre serves as a case study for other GBNs by demonstrating in an illustrative report for PROBONO, explaining the objectives and the tasks (tools) for creating a larger impact through social interventions. The theory behind Regenerative Cross-Pollination is that multiple actions within a defined area amplify their overall impact.

Tasks: Describe what tools, events, art happenings etc. are relevant for creating a GBN. If there is a way to illustrate the impact the collaboration has had on the ACRB development, it should be included.

7.4 Conclusion

Two social engagement activities that are in progress have been presented, namely the CERNA survey and the engagement activities in the Regenerative Centre with company NXT. The CERNA survey has been prepared and is planned to be completed by at least 50 participants (and as many as 400 participants) in early 2025. The NXT engagement activities are currently being prepared and will be deployed alongside regular Regenerative Centre monthly meetings in the remainder of 2024 and early 2025.

8 Prague LL Capacity building

8.1 Prague GBN Vision

Prague LL vision is closely interlinked with its contribution to the surrounding GBN, therefore the living lab vision can be listed here (as in D2.3.)

The vision of Prague Living Lab involves the dissemination of GBN through the application of present and future expertise in passive building solutions, smart energy management solutions aimed at improved efficiency, and advanced technologies such as digital twin. However, it is of utmost importance to maintain a clear understanding of what GBN truly entails.

It is crucial to identify the key stakeholders involved. GBN is not merely concerned with the technical aspects of buildings and their surroundings but also emphasises the engagement of citizens, the consideration of natural aspects, the significance of physical attributes, and the inclusion of the political dimension.

Policymakers play a pivotal role as they impact various aspects of public life within the district. Furthermore, the objective is to leverage the gained experience for future urban policy planning and provide support for the subsequent adoption of innovative practices.

This approach offers numerous advantages. Firstly, it reduces the negative environmental impact, enhances the quality of life for the neighbourhood residents, boosts economic performance, and leads to reduced operating costs in the long run. The beneficial impact of a green building neighbourhood on society can be substantial, resulting in increased satisfaction with the quality of life and the relationship with nature in the surroundings. Additionally, it improves air quality, enhances the city's resilience to climate change, and promotes safety and health for residents. Such an area becomes more attractive for additional investments, thereby generating economic benefits and creating new opportunities. The objective of Prague Living Lab is to engage citizens in this emerging trend and showcase new options for future comfortable urban living.

8.2 CERNA survey

A Climate and Energy Related Norms and Awareness (CERNA) survey is planned to be conducted among the citizens of Prague. Such a survey aims to investigate three main topics: awareness of the most effective energy-saving actions, perceived social norms, and the presence of pluralistic ignorance. The final analysis will help identify actionable steps to enhance citizens' attitudes and behaviours toward energy efficiency.

Harmon Research was the company awarded for the service, and the budget for the service is EUR 5.350 without a VAT for 600 respondents. The whole subcontracting process is being finalized within upcoming weeks. The service will be developed through online interviews with a questionnaire, previously structured and programmed by SIN, with an approximate length between 10 and 15 minutes.

8.3 User testing of a digital twin

One of the main focuses of the Prague Living Lab is Digital Twin development. Being the follower of Aarhus Living Lab, specific retrofit interventions will be determined according to the progress and development realised in Aarhus regarding the DT technology. The plan is to verify the proposed technology and planning tools through the DT and apply them later in the refurbishment of the selected building.

Prague LL proposes to allocate some of the Living Labs WP2 budgets to conduct professional user testing on the Digital Twin. Since this software will play a crucial role in the realisation of the GBN, its usability and interface need to be tested and adjusted accordingly as part of the development process. The possible methods of testing include one-on-one interviews or focus groups with test participants, whose feedback will be incorporated into the functionalities and design before the final launch. The timeline of this activity will be determined to be in alignment with the stages of development.

This activity involves potential users of the Digital Twin, such as relevant faculty members, or representatives of the urban planning department of Prague 6.

As the main focus of the Prague Living Lab is the development of the Digital Twin, which will influence the refurbishment of the chosen campus building, the usability of this tool needs to be of good quality. The Digital Twin will be a great asset in the future for planning the

development of the neighbourhood and as such, its interface has to be sensible and intuitive to its future users.

8.4 Conclusion

Two social engagement activities are currently under development, namely the CERNA survey and user testing of a digital twin. For the dissemination of the CERNA survey, the whole subcontracting process is being finalized within the upcoming weeks. The service will be developed through online interviews with a questionnaire previously structured and programmed by SIN. User testing of the digital twin is currently being prepared, and a more concrete timeline will be determined in alignment with the stages of the DT development.

9 Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable reported on the activities or tools relevant to Capacity Building that have occurred or that are planned to occur across the PROBONO's Living Labs. These activities are mostly related to social innovation, aiming for raising awareness and for promoting behavioural changes towards sustainable actions, especially energy efficiency. Furthermore, some examples take advantage of technological innovations that are being implemented, using them as an opportunity to address similar capacity building goals.

The initiatives present a set of diverse ways to address behavioural changes and energy efficiency, supporting capacity building in each Living Lab and providing examples that can be disseminated across PROBONO and beyond.

Key findings from this initial collation of activities are:

- The relevance of community engagement activities for successful planning and implementation of interventions.
- The benefits of adapting initiatives such as CERNA across the living labs to promote tailored communication about pro-environmental behaviours.
- The positive impact of the PROBONO project in the LLs, contributing to advancing ways of engaging and communicating, promoting innovative methods and tools that can be scaled up and/ or adopted beyond the life-span of the project.

For the next steps, discussions with the Living Labs will support the selection of the activities and tools that can be scaled up. They will include further assessment of gaps by testing PROBONO's findings about behaviour change with a sample of citizens from the wider community. Such selection of tools and initiatives will be key to develop a suite of Capacity Building tools, co-created between PROBONO's partners and communities.

References

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